

Neural Network-Based Box-Oriented Framework for Behavioral Modeling and Digital Predistortion of Power Amplifiers

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ABSTRACT This article presents a new box-oriented framework and training strategy that integrates conventional models with neural networks (NNs) for accurate power amplifier (PA) behavioral modeling and digital predistortion (DPD). Existing NN-based approaches rely solely on real-valued networks that overlook key complex-domain characteristics, and they attempt to learn all PA nonlinear distortions within the NN itself, resulting in unnecessarily high model complexity. To address these limitations, we propose a new technique that uses a simple conventional memory polynomial-based model to characterize the dominant PA distortions and a NN to characterize the remaining residual distortions. Following the framework, we introduce three new architectures: the feature-augmented simplified real-valued time-delay NN (SRTDNN), the generalized SRTDNN, and the parallel SRTDNN, combining a lightweight complex-valued polynomial model with a real-valued time-delay NN. In addition, we propose a joint training strategy to optimize both model components under different initialization schemes. Experimental validation using a 100 MHz 5G-NR OFDM signal and a Skyworks commercial PA shows that the proposed architectures achieve up to 1.1 dB improvement in normalized mean square error or a 45.5% reduction in model complexity compared to the state-of-the-art vector-decomposed long short-term memory (VDLSTM) in PA behavioral modeling. In DPD experiments, the proposed models achieve improvements up to 1.22 dB in adjacent channel power ratio and 1.07 dB in error vector magnitude over the VDLSTM. Moreover, the proposed joint training approach improves modeling performance by up to 1.6 dB compared to the fixed-training strategy employed in the state-of-the-art SARTDNN.

INDEX TERMS Behavioral modeling, box-oriented modeling, digital predistortion (DPD), dynamic nonlinear system, linearization, low complex, neural network (NN), power amplifier (PA).

I. INTRODUCTION

SERVING the growing demand for higher data rates with feasible power consumption, the accurate characterization and efficient linearization of radio frequency (RF) power amplifiers (PAs) have become increasingly challenging in

modern wireless communication systems. To achieve higher efficiency, PAs are usually operated closer to their saturation region; however, this often leads to significant nonlinear (NL) distortion at the PA output [1]. As a dynamic NL system, the PA introduces both static and dynamic NL

effects into the transmitted signal. The static NL effects, often referred to as memoryless or quasi-memoryless, characterize the narrowband amplitude-to-amplitude (AM/AM) and amplitude-to-phase (AM/PM) characteristics of the PA, whereas dynamic NL effects, commonly known as memory effects, become more pronounced as the signal bandwidth increases [1].

A. Prior Art

Generally, the behavior of dynamic NL systems such as PAs has been characterized with memory polynomial (MP)-based models, box-oriented models, and neural network (NN)-based models [1]. MP-based models can be seen as simplified forms of the Volterra series and are widely used for behavioral modeling and digital predistortion (DPD) of PAs. Well-known examples include the generalized memory polynomial (GMP), dynamic deviation reduction (DDR), and envelope memory polynomial (EMP) models [2]–[5]. Although these models offer considerable performance, their modeling accuracy is often limited by the inability to capture correlations between independent basis functions. Box-oriented models, on the other hand, aim to reduce the complexity of MP-based models and improve numerical stability [1]. They are typically constructed using some combination of a static NL system and a linear time-invariant (LTI) system, as seen in the Wiener, Hammerstein, and Wiener-Hammerstein models [6]–[11]. However, both MP-based and box-oriented models face inherent limitations that hinder performance improvement beyond a certain level [12]. With the advent of artificial NNs, NN-based PA models have recently demonstrated significant improvements over MP-based and box-oriented models [12]–[26].

In the literature, a wide range of NN architectures and training algorithms have been proposed for PA characterization and DPD modeling. In most NN-based approaches, the dynamic NL behavior of the PA is captured using current and multiple past inputs, a technique commonly referred to as time-delay neural network (TDNN). This framework is widely applied in most NN-based PA models [12]–[16]. For example, the real-valued time-delay NN (RVTDNN) model incorporates current and past in-phase and quadrature (I/Q) samples [13], whereas the augmented real-valued time-delay NN (ARVTDNN) model enhances performance and reduces complexity by integrating envelope-dependent features [12]. The residual real-valued time-delay NN (R2TDNN) leverages residual learning to independently model the linear and NL PA distortions [14]. In contrast, other architectures, such as long short-term memory (LSTM) and convolutional NN (CNN)-based models, have also been explored [15]–[18]. Despite their effectiveness, a common drawback of these NN-based models is their high computational and memory complexity, which hinders efficient hardware implementation. As a result, many studies have investigated methods to reduce complexity [20]–[26].

The simplified real-valued time-delay NN (SRTDNN) and simplified augmented real-valued time-delay NN (SARTDNN) architectures address this by decoupling the intricate NL characteristics of the PA into static and dynamic components, which are identified separately [22], [23]. Similarly, the authors in [24] employ a conventional MP model to generate basis functions that are subsequently used as fixed input features for a NN. This approach can be categorized as a feature-based cascading method, in which the MP stage serves as a fixed preprocessing step. In a related direction, the identification of static NL effects from modulated excitations has been utilized as a surrogate modeling approach to enhance DPD performance [26]. Furthermore, the vector-decomposed time-delay neural network (VDTDNN) and vector-decomposed long short-term memory (VDLSTM) architectures employ a vector decomposition approach, in which the envelope-dependent characteristics are first modeled, followed by phase reconstruction via a dedicated phase recovery block. The approaches VDTDNN, VDLSTM, R2TDNN, SRTDNN, and SARTDNN can be viewed as cascaded, residual, or multi-stage modeling techniques, with numerous other related methods also reported in the literature [27]–[30]. However, all the aforementioned NN-based models are real-valued, which inherently limits their ability to exploit complex domain information, such as conjugate components and phase relations.

B. Motivation

Since the input and output signals of the PA are represented as complex-valued I/Q samples in the baseband domain, a substantial portion of this critical information remains underutilized or completely overlooked in current real-valued NN-based PA and DPD models. Therefore, the primary motivation of this work is to incorporate complex domain information into the existing NN architectures, thereby aligning the NN models more closely with the physical characteristics of the PAs. In addition, we aim to leverage the conventional complex-valued MP-based models to extract the dominant portion of the intricate RF NL characteristics of the PA, allowing the NN to focus on modeling the residual NL characteristics not captured by the MP model. Conventional NN-based approaches often rely on an end-to-end learning, where all the complex RF PA NL characteristics are modeled by the NN itself, increasing its internal complexity [12]–[16]. To address this, our initial work introduced SRTDNN and SARTDNN, a box-oriented approach that decouples static NL effects from the NN learning process, enabling the NN to focus specifically on the dynamic NL behavior of the PA [22], [23]. Despite their effectiveness, these models had several limitations. First, their training strategy relied on a real-valued, static NL model, which prevented full exploitation of complex-domain information. Second, they were validated only on narrowband signals, leaving their performance on wider bandwidths untested. Finally, when the static NL model exhibits significant modeling errors, the

NN tends to focus on correcting these errors rather than improving overall performance, thereby limiting the benefit of the box-oriented modeling.

C. Contributions

This work introduces a box-oriented framework that integrates conventional models (CMs) with NNs for PA modeling and DPD, explicitly preserving complex-domain information through the CM block and enabling the systematic derivation of a family of flexible architectures.

Box-oriented framework: the proposed framework integrates CMs with NN models in a modular manner. The CM block is not restricted to a specific form and may be realized using memoryless polynomial models, MP-based models, or linear filtering structures, while the NN block may employ different architectures. Furthermore, the CM and NN blocks can be combined in multiple configurations, enabling the systematic derivation of a family of flexible architectures.

Proposed architectures: we introduce three different novel architectures following the framework, which provide different performance-complexity tradeoffs:

- **Generalized SRTDNN (G-SRTDNN):** generalizes the original SRTDNN by incorporating complex-valued CM with memory effects.
- **Feature augmented SRTDNN (FA-SRTDNN):** uses CM as a feature augmentation block, providing an abstract representation of dominant NL characteristics as a feature to the NN.
- **Parallel SRTDNN (PAR-SRTDNN):** explores parallel configurations where both CM and NN process the input signal simultaneously.

Shared memory modeling: unlike existing cascaded or feature-based approaches, where memory effects are mainly handled by a single modeling stage, the proposed framework enables a structured distribution of NL memory effects across both the CM and NN blocks. The CM block captures dominant, structured memory components, while the NN focuses on modeling complementary residual dynamics.

Complex-domain processing: unlike existing real-valued approaches, we incorporate a complex-valued CM block that preserves essential complex domain information typically lost in real-valued NN processing.

Training methodology: we propose a joint training strategy that simultaneously optimizes both CM and NN blocks under different initialization schemes. This approach addresses a key limitation of existing two-stage methods, where the NN often focus on correcting the errors in the conventional model rather than improving overall performance. The joint optimization paradigm applies to both complex-valued CMs and real-valued static NL models combined with NN architectures.

Experimental validation: we provide experimental validation using 100 MHz 5G-NR signals measured from a Skyworks commercial PA, demonstrating:

- **Superior performance:** significant improvements over state-of-the-art methods including VDTDNN, VDLSTM, and other reference approaches.
- **Bandwidth robustness:** consistent performance gains across range of bandwidths from 20 MHz to 100 MHz.
- **Practical applicability:** demonstrated effectiveness for modern wideband communication systems with significant complexity reduction compared to state-of-the-art methods.

Performance achievements: the proposed architectures achieve superior modeling accuracy and linearization performance across diverse scenarios, with notable improvements in normalized mean squared error (NMSE), adjacent channel power ratio (ACPR), and error vector magnitude (EVM) metrics, while maintaining computational efficiency by reducing model complexity compared to state-of-the-art methods.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides background on PA behavioral modeling, DPD modeling, and the box-oriented concept. Section III explains the proposed framework, and Section IV elaborates on the coefficient identification procedure. Section V presents a complexity analysis of the proposed architectures. The measurement setup and experimental results are discussed in Sections VI and VII, respectively. Finally, the paper is concluded in Section VIII.

II. Fundamentals

A. Behavioral Modeling of PA

Behavioral modeling characterizes the input-output relationship of the PA [1]. Let the baseband complex-valued input and output signal vectors of the PA be $\mathbf{x} = [x(1), \dots, x(N)]^T \in \mathbb{C}^N$ and $\mathbf{y} = [y(1), \dots, y(N)]^T \in \mathbb{C}^N$, where N denotes the number of samples in the baseband signal. We denote the PA model output as $\hat{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}; \Theta)$, parameterized by Θ , the set of PA model parameters. Then the PA behavioral modeling problem can be formulated as an optimization problem as

$$\min_{\Theta} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}; \Theta)), \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{L} denotes the loss function that quantifies the error between the measured output \mathbf{y} , and the modeled output $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$. Mean square error (MSE) is widely used in PA behavioral modeling [1], and is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |y(n) - \hat{y}(n)|^2, \quad (2)$$

where $|\cdot|$ denotes the absolute value operator.

B. Digital Predistortion (DPD)

The purpose of DPD is to pre-compensate the NL distortions introduced by the PA, aiming for a linear PA output. Instead

of passing the input \mathbf{x} directly to the PA, the signal is first pre-distorted by the DPD block, which approximates the time-domain inverse characteristics of the PA [1]. Accurate identification of the DPD function is therefore crucial for achieving effective linearization. In NN-based DPD models, three main learning architectures are commonly applied: indirect learning, iterative learning control, and backpropagation through a NN-based PA model [31]–[33]. In this work, we adopt the latter approach to identify the DPD coefficients. Accordingly, the DPD identification problem can be formulated as an optimization problem as

$$\min_{\Phi} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{pd}}; \Phi)), \quad (3)$$

where Φ denotes the DPD model parameters, $\mathbf{x}_{\text{pd}} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ is the complex-valued discrete-time predistorted signal, and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ denotes the gain-normalized PA model output.

C. Box-Oriented Modeling for NNs

The distortions introduced by the PA consist of several components: static NL effects, linear memory effects, and NL memory effects. Learning all these distortions solely with a NN demands high internal complexity. Among them, the static NL effects usually dominate and can be efficiently modeled using polynomial-based methods or moving average techniques [1]. By isolating this significant portion of the distortions, the NN only needs to learn the residual distortions. This strategy reduces the number of neurons in the hidden layers, thereby lowering the overall NN complexity [22], [23]. Conceptually, this approach combines elements of box-oriented and NN-based modeling. In a cascaded box-oriented model, the PA output can be expressed as the composition of static and dynamic NL effects as

$$\hat{y}(n) = f_{\text{dyn}}(z(n), z(n-1), \dots, z(n-M)), \quad (4)$$

where $z(n)$ denotes the static NL model output, with $z(n) = f_{\text{st}}(x(n))$; $z(n-m)$ for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ denote the corresponding past samples. Here, f_{st} and f_{dyn} denote the static and dynamic behavioral characteristics of the PA, respectively. Once f_{st} is identified, the residual output primarily contains the dynamic NL characteristics, including both linear and NL memory effects. Modeling f_{dyn} is considerably simpler than learning the entire PA characteristics, which reduces the burden placed on the NN.

III. PROPOSED BOX-ORIENTED FRAMEWORK

A. Proposed Architectures

We propose three novel architectures to overcome the limitations of existing NN-based box-oriented approaches: FA-SRTDNN, G-SRTDNN, and PAR-SRTDNN. For clarity and generality, we illustrate each architecture using a combination of a CM and a NN block. The CM block can be implemented using any conventional model, such as an MP-based model, a real-valued polynomial model, a moving-average model, or even a filter. Similarly, the NN block can adopt any architecture depending on the requirement.

FIGURE 1. Block diagrams of the proposed box-oriented architectures. (a) Feature augmented-SRTDNN architecture. (b) Generalized-SRTDNN architecture. (c) Parallel-SRTDNN architecture.

1) Feature Augmented-SRTDNN

The FA-SRTDNN architecture incorporates the CM block as a feature augmentation block for the NN. The CM block processes the current and M_1 past samples ($M_1 \leq M$), to extract informative features that provide an abstract representation of the dynamic NL characteristics of the PA. These features reduce the modeling burden on the NN by simplifying its internal complexity. As illustrated in Fig. 1a, both the original inputs and the augmented features are fed into the NN, enabling it to refine any modeling inaccuracies introduced by the CM. The output of the CM, denoted as $z(n) \in \mathbb{C}$ can be written as

$$z(n) = f_{\text{CM}}(x(n), x(n-1), \dots, x(n-M_1)), \quad (5)$$

where $x(n)$ denotes the complex-valued input signal, and $x(n-m)$ for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M_1$ denote the past samples for M_1 memory taps. The function of the CM is denoted as f_{CM} . The NN then takes CM output together with the current and M past input samples, represented in real-valued form. Therefore, the final NN output $\hat{y}(n)$ can be expressed as

$$\hat{y}(n) = f_{\text{NN}}\left(z^I(n), x^I(n), x^I(n-1), \dots, x^I(n-M), \right. \\ \left. z^Q(n), x^Q(n), x^Q(n-1), \dots, x^Q(n-M)\right), \quad (6)$$

where $x^I(n)$ and $x^Q(n)$ denote the I/Q components of the complex-valued input signal $x(n)$ (i.e. $x(n) = x^I(n) + jx^Q(n)$); $x^I(n-m)$ and $x^Q(n-m)$ for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ denote the I/Q components of past samples; $z^I(n)$ and $z^Q(n)$ denote the I/Q components of the complex-valued output $z(n)$ of the CM block. The function of the NN is denoted as f_{NN} . It is worth noting that, although the NN operates on real-valued inputs, the complex-domain information is preserved through $z(n)$, since the CM performs the complex-valued processing.

2) Generalized-SRTDNN

We extend the SRTDNN architecture by introducing memory to the CM block. In the cascaded setup, the first processing block can be either the CM or NN. Here, we formulate the equations for the case where CM precedes the NN. The current and M_1 past input samples ($M_1 < M$) are processed by the CM, which produces the output $z(n)$, similarly to (5). Then the $z(n)$ and its M delayed versions are sent to the NN, which produces the final output $\hat{y}(n)$, expressed as

$$\hat{y}(n) = f_{\text{NN}}\left(z^I(n), z^I(n-1), \dots, z^I(n-M), z^Q(n), z^Q(n-1), \dots, z^Q(n-M)\right), \quad (7)$$

where $z^I(n)$ and $z^Q(n)$ denote the I/Q components of the complex-valued CM output $z(n)$; $z^I(n-m)$ and $z^Q(n-m)$ for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ denotes the I/Q components of its past samples.

3) Parallel-SRTDNN

We propose the PAR-SRTDNN architecture, where the CM and NN blocks operate in parallel. In this configuration, the current and past input samples are simultaneously processed by both the CM and NN blocks, and their outputs are combined through addition to generate the final output. This parallel combination enables the NN to effectively complement any modeling errors of the CM. The output of the CM, $z_1(n)$ can be expressed as in (5), while the output of the NN, $z_2(n)$ can be expressed as

$$z_2(n) = f_{\text{NN}}\left(x^I(n), x^I(n-1), \dots, x^I(n-M), x^Q(n), x^Q(n-1), \dots, x^Q(n-M)\right). \quad (8)$$

Then the final model output $y(n)$ can be expressed as

$$\hat{y}(n) = z_1(n) + z_2(n). \quad (9)$$

B. CM With Real-Valued Memoryless Polynomials

The purpose of CM block is to characterize the dominant NL effects of the PA using a simple conventional model. Since the static NL effects are the primary contributors to PA distortion, memoryless models offer a favorable performance-complexity tradeoff. Among the viable choices, real-valued polynomial models are particularly suitable, as demonstrated

FIGURE 2. Block diagram of real-valued memoryless polynomial-based CM.

in [22]. As described in the architectures above, the input and output vectors of the CM are denoted as $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ and $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{C}^N$, respectively. As implied by the term “memoryless”, the current output $z(n)$ depends solely on the current input $x(n)$ for $n = 1, \dots, N$. To model the static AM/AM and AM/PM characteristics, two independent real-valued polynomials can be applied as

$$\frac{|z(n)|}{|x(n)|} = A_G(|x(n)|) = \mathbf{a}^\top \nu_A(|x(n)|), \quad (10)$$

$$\angle z(n) - \angle x(n) = \Phi_G(|x(n)|) = \mathbf{p}^\top \nu_\Phi(|x(n)|), \quad (11)$$

where A_G and Φ_G denote the static AM/AM and AM/PM characteristics, respectively, and both are envelope-dependent complex gain functions. K_1 and K_2 denote the degrees of the static AM/AM and AM/PM polynomial models, and \angle indicates the angle operation. The real-valued coefficient vectors associated with these polynomial functions are defined as $\mathbf{a} = [a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{K_1}]^\top$ and $\mathbf{p} = [p_0, p_1, \dots, p_{K_2}]^\top$. The corresponding polynomial basis vectors are given by

$$\nu_A(|x(n)|) = [1, |x(n)|, |x(n)|^2, \dots, |x(n)|^{K_1+1}]^\top, \quad (12)$$

$$\nu_\Phi(|x(n)|) = [1, |x(n)|, |x(n)|^2, \dots, |x(n)|^{K_2+1}]^\top. \quad (13)$$

Using (10) and (11), the complex-valued final output of the CM block, $z(n)$ can be expressed as

$$z(n) = |x(n)| A_G(|x(n)|) e^{j(\Phi_G(|x(n)|) + \angle x(n))}. \quad (14)$$

Fig. 2 illustrates the block diagram of the described real-valued memoryless polynomial CM, where $C2P$ and $P2C$ blocks denote the Cartesian-to-Polar and Polar-to-Cartesian conversions, respectively. The main advantage of this approach is that the AM/AM and AM/PM characteristics are modeled independently using separate polynomials, allowing each to capture their distinct NL characteristics more accurately. On the other hand, a limitation is that the model operates in the real-valued domain, potentially discarding inherent complex-domain information.

C. CM With Cross-Term Memory Polynomials

A more general option is to implement the CM block using a complex-valued MP-based model, such as MP, GMP,

EMP, or DDR. Unlike memoryless real-valued polynomial models, this formulation offers greater flexibility, allowing the CM to be either memoryless or memory-dependent. More importantly, complex-valued models preserve the full complex-domain information, which real-valued models often overlook. This allows the model to leverage conjugate information, amplitude–phase relations, and other interactions in the complex domain. In this work, we illustrate the approach using cross-term MP models; however, any of the aforementioned model types can be employed. The output of the cross-term MP, $z(n)$ can be expressed as

$$z(n) = \mathbf{a}^T \mathbf{x}_n + \sum_{p=1}^{P-1} \mathbf{x}_n^T \mathbf{B}_p \psi_{p,n}, \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{x}_n denotes the vector of the current and M_1 past complex-valued input samples, with M_1 representing the memory depth of the CM block. It is defined as $\mathbf{x}_n = [x(n), x(n-1), \dots, x(n-M_1)]^T$. The vector $\psi_{p,n} \in \mathbb{R}^{M_1+1}$ contains the corresponding envelope terms for NL order $p = 1, 2, \dots, P-1$, with P denoting the maximum degree of the CM block, and is defined as

$$\psi_{p,n} = [|x(n)|^p, |x(n-1)|^p, \dots, |x(n-M_1)|^p]^T. \quad (16)$$

The linear coefficients vector $\mathbf{a}^T \in \mathbb{C}^{M_1+1}$ and NL coefficient matrices $\mathbf{B}_p \in \mathbb{C}^{(M_1+1) \times (M_1+1)}$, for $p = 1, 2, \dots, P-1$, defines the contributions of linear and NL terms, respectively. The cross-term MP model processes the current input $x(n)$ and its M_1 delayed versions to produce the output $z(n)$, enabling the CM to capture a portion of the system memory and thereby reducing the modeling burden of the NN.

D. NN With MLP-Based Architectures

The purpose of this block is to characterize the residual NL effects of the PA that remain after the CM has captured the dominant static and low-order dynamic NL effects. Due to the complex correlations among the basis functions of the CM, a residual error persists that cannot be adequately modeled using polynomials alone. Thus, a NN is well-suited to characterize the residual errors due to its high modeling capacity and flexibility. One can adopt an NN architecture tailored to the PA and the input signal. The input to NN depends on both the specific NN type and the configuration, as shown in Fig. 1. For analysis, we consider the G-SRTDNN architecture shown in Fig. 1b, employing an multilayer perceptron (MLP)-based NN model.

We consider a TDNN structure to account for the memory effects of the PA. As illustrated in Fig. 1b, the NN input consists of the current output of the CM block, $z(n)$, along with its M delayed versions. To enhance the modeling of NL memory effects, envelope-dependent features can be included in addition to the I/Q components, i.e., $|z(n-m)|^k$ for $m = 0, 1, \dots, M$ and $k = 1, \dots, K$. Therefore, we form the feature vector $\bar{\mathbf{z}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(K+2)(M+1)}$ as input to the NN,

FIGURE 3. Block diagram of the real-valued MLP-based NN architecture.

expressed as

$$\bar{\mathbf{z}} = \left[z^I(n-m), z^Q(n-m), |z(n-m)|^k \right. \\ \left. : m = 0, \dots, M, k = 1, \dots, K \right]^T. \quad (17)$$

The input feature vector $\bar{\mathbf{z}}$ is then passed through the MLP-based NN with H fully connected layers. The output of the h^{th} hidden layer for $h = 1, 2, \dots, H$, is denoted as $\mathbf{y}^{(h)}$ and can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{y}^{(h)} = \mathcal{F}_h \left(\mathbf{W}^{(h)} \mathbf{y}^{(h-1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(h)} \right), \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{W}^{(h)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h \times N_{h-1}}$, $\mathbf{b}^{(h)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h}$ and \mathcal{F}_h denote the weight matrix, bias vector, and activation function of h^{th} hidden layer, respectively. N_h denotes the number of neurons in the h^{th} hidden layer, and $h = 0$ denotes the input layer. Thus, for the input layer, we have $\mathbf{y}^{(0)} = \bar{\mathbf{z}}$, and $N_0 = (K+2)(M+1)$. Finally, the output of the last hidden layer (i.e., $h = H$) is passed through the output layer with two neurons and a linear activation function, producing the final output of the NN block, expressed as

$$\left[\hat{y}^I(n), \hat{y}^Q(n) \right] = \mathbf{W}^{(o)} \mathbf{y}^{(H)} + \mathbf{b}^{(o)}, \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{W}^{(o)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times N_H}$, $\mathbf{b}^{(o)} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denote the weight matrix and bias vector of the output layer, respectively. The outputs $\hat{y}^I(n)$ and $\hat{y}^Q(n)$ denote the I/Q components of model output, $\hat{y}(n)$, where $\hat{y}(n) = \hat{y}^I(n) + j\hat{y}^Q(n)$. The overall MLP-based NN architecture is illustrated in Fig. 3.

IV. PROPOSED COEFFICIENT IDENTIFICATION

In [22], the static NL model coefficients are determined using the least-squares method, after which the NN coefficients are optimized while keeping the static NL model coefficients fixed. This strategy, however, limits performance because the NN has a reduced degree of freedom to correct modeling

FIGURE 4. Joint optimization of the DPD coefficients via backpropagating through the PA model. $\mathbf{x}_{pd} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ denotes the predistorted complex-valued signal. The backpropagation path is shown in blue arrow.

errors in the static NL model during training. Simulation results show that instead of fixing the coefficients, allowing them to adapt jointly with the NN using a gradient-based optimizer improves performance. Therefore, we propose a joint optimization strategy in which the CM and NN coefficients are trained simultaneously using a gradient-based NN optimizer.

The baseband input and measured PA output can be directly used for PA behavioral modeling (see Section II). In contrast, DPD identification can be performed using different approaches. In this work, we adopt backpropagation through a PA model learning strategy, where a PA model is first identified and the error is backpropagated through it to the DPD, enabling optimization of its coefficients [32]. Here, the MSE loss between the gain-normalized PA model output, $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, and the input signal, \mathbf{x} , is computed using (3). The gradients of this loss with respect to the DPD model parameters are then obtained by backpropagating the error through the PA model. The PA model coefficients are kept fixed during the optimization of the DPD coefficients. Considering a cross-term MP model as the CM and MLP architecture for the NN, we denote the CM and NN coefficients as Φ_{CM} and Φ_{NN} respectively, expressed as

$$\Phi_{CM} = [\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{B}_1, \mathbf{B}_2, \dots, \mathbf{B}_{P-1}],$$

$$\Phi_{NN} = [\mathbf{W}^{(h)}, \mathbf{b}^{(h)}, \mathbf{W}^{(o)}, \mathbf{b}^{(o)}].$$

Similarly, we denote the coefficients of the PA model as Φ_{PA} . The linearization objective is to update the DPD model coefficients to minimize the MSE between \mathbf{x} and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$. The block diagram in Fig. 4 illustrates the DPD coefficients optimization via backpropagating through the PA model.

A. Joint Optimization of CM and NN via Gradient-Based Methods

In this approach, the CM and NN coefficients, i.e., Φ_{CM} and Φ_{NN} , are optimized jointly. We illustrate the identification strategy for PA behavioral modeling; a similar approach can be applied for DPD identification. Let the measured baseband discrete-time complex-valued input and output signals of the PA be denoted as $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ and $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^N$, respectively. The model output vector $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ is obtained during the

forward pass through the model. For example, in the case of the G-SRTDNN architecture, $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ can be derived using (15), (17), (18), and (19). The coefficients, Φ_{CM} and Φ_{NN} , are then updated jointly by minimizing the MSE between the measured output \mathbf{y} and the modeled output $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, as defined in (2).

To optimize the coefficients, we use the Adam optimizer. The coefficients, Φ_{CM} and Φ_{NN} , are initialized using a uniform distribution over the range $[-0.8, 0.8]$. This initialization preserves symmetry around zero, thereby avoiding biased updates, and is consistent with the initialization in [12]. Then, the Adam optimizer is initialized with its default parameters [34]. At each iteration k , the gradient of the MSE loss function, $\nabla_{\theta_k} \mathcal{L}_{MSE}$, is computed via backpropagation with respect to the parameter vector $\theta = \{\Phi_{CM}, \Phi_{NN}\}$. The first and second moment estimates, μ_k and ν_k , are updated and corrected for bias to obtain $\hat{\mu}_k$ and $\hat{\nu}_k$ as defined in [34]. Finally, the learning rate lr_k is adjusted based on the scheduling criteria and parameters described in Section VI-D. This procedure is repeated iteratively over the specified number of training epochs.

B. Least-Squares Initialization of CM for Joint Optimization

The CM coefficients are initialized using the least-squares solution instead of random initialization. For the real-valued polynomial-based CM, the least-squares identification follows the method described in [22]. For the cross-term MP-based CM, the coefficients are obtained by solving the linear system given by

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}_{ct} \Phi_{CM}, \quad (20)$$

where \mathbf{y} denotes the measured baseband PA output and \mathbf{X}_{ct} denotes the observation matrix of the cross-term MP model, constructed by stacking the corresponding terms defined in (15). Let the estimation error be denoted as $e(n) = y(n) - \hat{y}(n)$, where $\hat{y}(n)$ is the estimated output of the above linear system. The least-squares solution that minimizes the error vector $\mathbf{e} = [e(1), e(2), \dots, e(N)]$ is given by

$$\Phi_{CM}^{(0)} = (\mathbf{X}_{ct}^H \mathbf{X}_{ct})^{-1} \mathbf{X}_{ct}^H \mathbf{y}. \quad (21)$$

The CM coefficients are then initialized with $\Phi_{CM}^{(0)}$, while the NN coefficients are initialized using the same uniform random distribution. The complete parameter set, θ is then optimized using the Adam optimizer, with the learning rate adjusted, as described previously. The overall training procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1. f_{model} denotes the functionality of the model in general for all the architectures.

V. COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

This section presents a complexity analysis of the proposed architectures. The complexity of a NN-based model is typically evaluated using two primary metrics: memory requirements, measured by the number of coefficients, and computational complexity, measured by the number of floating

Algorithm 1 Proposed joint optimization algorithm

Initialization:

- 1) Measurements: $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ and $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^N$.
- 2) Model parameters: $P, M_1, M, K, H, \{\mathcal{F}_h, N_h\}_{h=1}^H$.
- 3) Initialize $\Phi_{\text{CM}}^{(0)}$ as

$$\Phi_{\text{CM}}^{(0)} = \begin{cases} \mathcal{U}(-0.8, 0.8), & \text{if random init} \\ (\mathbf{X}_{\text{ct}}^H \mathbf{X}_{\text{ct}})^{-1} \mathbf{X}_{\text{ct}}^H \mathbf{y}, & \text{if least-squares init} \end{cases}$$
- 4) Initialize $\Phi_{\text{NN}}^{(0)} = \mathcal{U}(-0.8, 0.8)$
- 5) Set $\theta_0 = \{\Phi_{\text{CM}}^{(0)}, \Phi_{\text{NN}}^{(0)}\}$
- 6) Initialize Adam: $\beta_1 = 0.9, \beta_2 = 0.999, \epsilon = 10^{-8}, lr_0 = 10^{-3}, \mu_0 = 0, \nu_0 = 0$

Optimization:

- 1) **For** $k = 0, 1, \dots, \text{epochs} - 1$ **do**
 - a) Forward pass: $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = f_{\text{model}}(\mathbf{x}; \theta_k)$
 - b) Compute loss: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |y(n) - \hat{y}(n)|^2$
 - c) Compute gradient: $\nabla_{\theta_k} \mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}} \leftarrow \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}}}{\partial \theta_k}$
 - d) Update moments:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_k &= \beta_1 \mu_{k-1} + (1 - \beta_1) \nabla_{\theta_k} \mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}}, \\ \nu_k &= \beta_2 \nu_{k-1} + (1 - \beta_2) (\nabla_{\theta_k} \mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}})^2 \end{aligned}$$
 - e) Bias correction: $\hat{\mu}_k = \frac{\mu_k}{1 - \beta_1^k}, \quad \hat{\nu}_k = \frac{\nu_k}{1 - \beta_2^k}$
 - f) Parameter update:

$$\theta_{k+1} = \theta_k - \frac{lr_k \hat{\mu}_k}{\sqrt{\hat{\nu}_k} + \epsilon}$$
 - g) Update learning rate: $lr_{k+1} \leftarrow \text{schedule}(lr_k)$
 - 2) **End For**
-

point operations (FLOPs). Computational complexity can be analyzed from two perspectives: training and inference. In NN complexity analysis, it is commonly approximated that one backward pass requires roughly the same effort as two forward passes, implying that the total training complexity is about three times the inference complexity [35]. Consequently, inference complexity is approximately proportional to training complexity. Moreover, since the training is performed offline in this framework, the practical focus is on inference complexity. Therefore, we consider inference complexity the primary metric, while training complexity is treated as indirectly proportional, ensuring that the comparative analysis remains valid across different architectures. In the proposed architectures, two blocks contribute to the overall complexity: the CM and the NN block. Without loss of generality, we consider the CM as a cross-term MP model, and the NN as a MLP model. Since cross-term MP models employ complex-valued coefficients, we account for this by considering real-valued coefficients in our calculations to

ensure comparability with other architectures. Therefore, the total number of coefficients is the sum of the real-valued coefficients from each block. We denote the number of coefficients in the CM block as C_{cm} , which can be expressed as

$$C_{\text{cm}} = 2(M_1 + 1) \left(1 + (M_1 + 1)(P - 1) \right). \quad (22)$$

The number of coefficients in the MLP-based NN block, denoted as C_{nn} , can be expressed as

$$C_{\text{nn}} = \sum_{h=1}^H (N_{h-1} + 1) N_h + 2(N_H + 1), \quad (23)$$

where N_0 denotes the number of neurons in the input layer, which varies according to specific architecture. For instance, $N_0 = (M + 1)(K + 2)$ for the FA-SRTDNN architecture. Therefore, the total number of coefficients, denoted as C , can be expressed as

$$C = C_{\text{cm}} + C_{\text{nn}}. \quad (24)$$

The total inference FLOPs of the proposed architectures can be obtained by summing the FLOPs from both the CM and NN blocks. The number of FLOPs for the CM is straightforward, and can be expressed as $F_{\text{cm}} = 8C_{\text{cm}}$ [36]. The number of FLOPs required for the MLP NN block depends on two main operations: matrix computations and activation function evaluations. The number of FLOPs required for the matrix computations, denoted as F_{W} , can be expressed as

$$F_{\text{W}} = 4N_H + \sum_{h=1}^H 2N_{h-1}N_h. \quad (25)$$

Let F_{σ} denote the FLOPs required for the activation function of a single neuron. For commonly used activation functions such as rectified linear unit (ReLU), leaky ReLU, and tangent sigmoid (Tanh), the average value of F_{σ} are approximately 2, 3 and 13, respectively [16]. The FLOPs required for the NN block, denoted as F_{nn} , can be computed as

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\text{nn}} &= F_{\text{W}} + \sum_{h=1}^H F_{\sigma} N_h \\ &= 4N_H + \sum_{h=1}^H N_h (2N_{h-1} + F_{\sigma}). \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Finally, the total inference FLOPs required for the proposed architecture can be obtained as

$$F = F_{\text{cm}} + F_{\text{nn}}. \quad (27)$$

A similar complexity analysis can be applied to all proposed architectures. The number of coefficients and FLOPs for the proposed architectures and benchmark models are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1. The complexity calculations for the proposed and reference models.

Model	Number of coefficients	Number of FLOPs
GMP [2]	$2((M_a + 1)K_a + (M_b + 1)K_bP_b + (M_c + 1)K_cQ_c)$	$8((M_a + 1)K_a + (M_b + 1)K_bP_b + (M_c + 1)K_cQ_c)$
R2TDNN [14]	$(2(M + 1) + 1)N_1 + \sum_{h=2}^H(N_{h-1} + 1)N_h + 2(N_H + 1)$	$4N_H + 2(M + 1)N_1 + \sum_{h=2}^H N_h(2N_{h-1} + F_\sigma) + 2$
VDTDNN [20]	$(P(M + 1) + 5)N_1 + 4(M + 1)$	$(2P(M + 1) + F_\sigma)N_1 + 8(N_1 + M) + 12$
VDLSTM [21]	$4(L^2 + 2ML + 3L)$	$8L^2 + 12L(M + 1) + 4LF_\sigma + 10(M + 1)$
SARTDNN [22]	$(K_1 + K_2 + 2) + ((K + 2)(M + 1) + 1)N_1 + 2(N_H + 1) + \sum_{h=2}^H(N_{h-1} + 1)N_h$	$21 + 2(K_1 + K_2) + 2(K + 2)(M + 1)N_1 + \max(K_2, K_2) + 4N_H + \sum_{h=2}^H N_h(2N_{h-1} + F_\sigma)$
Proposed architectures	$2(M_1 + 1) + 2(M_1 + 1)^2(P - 1) + 2(N_H + 1) + \sum_{h=1}^H(N_{h-1} + 1)N_h$	$8(M_1 + 1) + 8(M_1 + 1)^2(P - 1) + 4N_H + \sum_{h=1}^H N_h(2N_{h-1} + F_\sigma)$

K_a, K_b, K_c represent the NL orders for aligned, lagging, and leading envelopes, M_a, M_b, M_c represent the memory depths for aligned, lagging, and leading envelopes, P_b, Q_c represent the cross-term orders for lagging and leading envelopes [2]. L represents the number of neurons in the LSTM layer. All other parameters retain their previous definitions. For each proposed architecture, N_0 depends on the selected features and configuration.

VI. MEASUREMENT SETUP

A. The PA Characteristics and the Baseband Signal

To evaluate the performance of the proposed architectures, we use the measurement procedure shown in Fig. 5a. The device under test (DUT) is the SKY66320-11 PA from Skyworks Inc., a high-efficiency wide instantaneous bandwidth PA designed for micro and macro base stations [38]. The PA’s evaluation board was placed inside a metallic casing to facilitate safer and convenient handling in the laboratory environment. The PA is designed to operate in the 3.6 GHz-3.8 GHz frequency range, and all measurements were conducted at a center frequency of 3.7 GHz. The device was biased with a 5 V supply voltage, 5 V bias voltage, and a 2 V enable voltage. At the selected operating point, the PA delivers an average output power of 27 dBm. The measured output saturation power (P_{sat}) of the PA is approximately 36.2 dBm, corresponding to approximately 9.2 dB output backoff at the operating point. The test signal is a 100 MHz orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) waveform, modulated using 64-QAM with a subcarrier spacing of 30 kHz. It has a 10.3 dB peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) and a baseband sampling rate of 614.4 MHz, oversampled with a factor of 5.

B. Experimental Setup

The test signal is generated using the MATLAB 5G Toolbox [39] and transferred to the Keysight M8190A arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) via USB connection, which produces the corresponding RF signal as shown in Fig. 5a. The AWG output is then fed to the Keysight E8267D performance vector signal generator (PSG) for analog upconversion to the 3.7 GHz carrier frequency. The PSG is used to adjust the power level to drive the PA into the NL region, and operate under the intended operating conditions. The upconverted and power-adjusted RF signal is then fed to the PA. The PA output is attenuated using a fixed attenuator and fed into the Keysight N9040B UXA spectrum analyzer to prevent overdriving the input of the analyzer. Finally, we use the

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 5. (a) Block diagram of the measurement procedure. (b) Photograph of the measurement setup.

FIGURE 6. (a) Learning architectures used for baseband and RF processing in PA behavioral modeling, and (b) DPD modeling. The dashed highlighted blocks represent baseband processing performed using MATLAB and PyTorch.

Keysight 89600 Vector Signal Analyzer (VSA) software to download the baseband PA output signal into MATLAB. A photograph of the measurement system is shown in Fig. 5b. The baseband PA input and output signals are then time-synchronized and processed using the PyTorch framework for PA behavioral modeling and DPD modeling. Figs. 6a and 6b illustrate the block diagrams of the learning architectures applied during baseband and RF processing for behavioral modeling and DPD modeling, respectively.

C. Performance Metrics

The performance of behavioral modeling is evaluated in the time domain using the NMSE, defined as

$$\text{NMSE (dB)} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N |y(n) - \hat{y}(n)|^2}{\sum_{n=1}^N |y(n)|^2} \right). \quad (28)$$

The DPD performance is evaluated in the frequency domain, in-band using the EVM and out-of-band using the ACPR. These metrics are defined as

$$\text{ACPR (dBc)} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{P_{\text{adj}}}{P_{\text{main}}} \right), \quad (29)$$

$$\text{EVM (dB)} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N |s(n) - \hat{s}(n)|^2}{\sum_{n=1}^N |s(n)|^2}} \right), \quad (30)$$

where P_{main} denotes the total power within the main channel, and P_{adj} denotes the maximum power of the two adjacent

channels. $s(n)$ and $\hat{s}(n)$ denote the reference and demodulated constellation points, respectively.

D. Training, Validation, and Testing of the Models

The baseband input and output signals of the PA are acquired through the measurement setup and used to train the models offline. The coefficient optimization of the proposed architectures is performed using Algorithm 1. The training data consist of I/Q samples corresponding to one OFDM slot, which is divided into 60% for training and 40% for validation. An independent dataset, also corresponding to one OFDM slot, is used for testing. To enhance the numerical stability of the NN learning, we use standard deviation (STD) normalization. The Adam optimizer is initialized with its default hyperparameters, verified experimentally to be effective: $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, and $\epsilon = 10^{-8}$, along with an initial learning rate, $lr_0 = 10^{-3}$. The NN models are trained for 100 epochs, with a batch size of 256, using a learning rate scheduler that reduces the learning rate by a factor of 0.5 if the validation MSE does not improve for 10 consecutive epochs.

VII. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

A. Comparison of Behavioral Modeling Performance

We evaluate the behavioral modeling performance of proposed architectures and compare against state-of-the-art techniques, GMP [2], R2TDNN [14], VDTDNN [20], VDLSTM [21], and SARTDNN [22]. The modeling performance is assessed using the NMSE, as defined in (28). All models are implemented in the PyTorch framework using the baseband input and output signals of the PA, acquired through the measurement setup described in Section VI.

The memory depth for the 100 MHz signal bandwidth is selected based on an experimental performance-complexity tradeoff analysis. Table 2 reports the NMSE performance and the number of FLOPs as a function of the memory depth, evaluated using two benchmark models, the GMP and the R2TDNN. Here, the memory depth, M denotes the number of delayed input samples; for the GMP, this corresponds to the maximum lag across all polynomial branches. The results indicate that increasing the memory depth up to $M = 3$ yields substantial improvements in NMSE, whereas further increases result in only marginal performance gains (less than 0.2 dB) at a significantly higher computational cost. Accordingly, a memory depth of $M = 3$ is selected for the 100 MHz signal.

The remaining model-specific parameters are summarized in Table 3, following the configurations reported in the respective references, and further refined through experimental hyperparameter tuning for our PA measurements. To ensure a fair comparison, we train all NN-based models, including the proposed ones with randomly initialized weights, using the training parameters specified in Section VI-D. The GMP coefficients are identified using the least squares method.

TABLE 2. Memory depth versus performance-complexity tradeoff for the 100 MHz signal bandwidth.

Model	Metric	Memory depth (M)					
		0	1	2	3	4	5
GMP	NMSE (dB)	-27.05	-35.07	-37.46	-38.17	-38.28	-38.35
	FLOPs	54	206	454	798	1238	1774
R2TDNN	NMSE (dB)	-28.02	-36.08	-38.32	-39.09	-39.17	-39.24
	FLOPs	629	857	1085	1313	1541	1769

TABLE 3. Parameter settings for PA behavioral modeling and DPD for the proposed and reference models.

Model	Parameter settings
GMP [2]	$M_a = 3, K_a = 7, M_b = 2, K_b = 6, P_b = 2,$ $M_c = 2, K_c = 6, Q_c = 2$
R2TDNN [14]	features = $[x^I, x^Q], H = 1, \sigma_1 = \text{Leaky_ReLU}, N_1 = 57$
SARTDNN [22]	features = $[x^I, x^Q, x , x ^2, x ^3], H = 1, \sigma_1 = \text{Tanh},$ $N_1 = 26, K_1 = 9, K_2 = 8$
VDTDNN [20]	features = $[x , x ^2, x ^3], H = 1, \sigma_1 = \text{ABS}, N_1 = 40$
VDLSTM [21]	features = $[x^I, x^Q], H = 1, \sigma_1 = \text{Tanh}, L = 9$
FA-SRTDNN	features = $[x^I, x^Q, x , x ^2, x ^3], M_1 = 3, P = 5,$ $H = 1, N_1 = 20, \sigma_1 = \text{Tanh}$
G-SRTDNN	features = $[x^I, x^Q, x , x ^2, x ^3], M_1 = 1, P = 7, H = 1,$ $N_1 = 25, \sigma_1 = \text{Tanh}$
PAR-SRTDNN	features = $[x^I, x^Q, x , x ^2, x ^3], M_1 = 3, P = 1$ $H = 1, N_1 = 27, \sigma_1 = \text{Tanh}$

Fig. 7 illustrates the convergence of the proposed and reference NN-based models. The proposed models achieve the lowest validation MSE and converge faster than the reference methods. This behavior results from the box-oriented structure, where CM captures the dominant PA characteristics, and allows the NN to focus on the residual NL effects. In particular, compared to SARTDNN, the proposed cross-term MP-based CM models achieve a lower validation MSE, demonstrating the effectiveness of complex domain learning in the proposed box-oriented architectures.

We then compare the modeling performance of the proposed and reference models in terms of parameter count. Figure 8 presents the test NMSE obtained on an independent dataset as a function of the number of real-valued coefficients for each model. The number of model coefficients is altered by varying the number of hidden-layer neurons, N_1 . The results demonstrate that the proposed architectures achieve either improved performance for a given model complexity or comparable performance with significantly fewer parameters. To further illustrate this, we consider two scenarios. In the first scenario, all models exhibit similar performance, with approximately -40 dB NMSE. We compare their corresponding number of coefficients, as summarized in Table 4. To quantify the complexity reduction, we define the metric

FIGURE 7. Comparison of training convergence of proposed and reference PA behavioral models.

complexity reduction ratio (CRR) as

$$CRR (\%) = \left(1 - \frac{C_{\text{prop}}}{C_{\text{ref}}}\right) \times 100, \quad (31)$$

where C_{prop} and C_{ref} denote the number of real-valued coefficients in the proposed and reference models, respectively. The proposed architectures achieve approximately -40 dB NMSE with a smaller number of coefficients compared to reference models, except for the GMP. However, the GMP exhibits a performance gap of around 2 dB, and further increasing its number of parameters does not yield any noticeable performance improvement. Among the proposed architectures, the G-SRTDNN shows the smallest number of coefficients of 353, and PAR-SRTDNN demonstrates the lowest computational complexity with 887 FLOPs. The CRR of the PAR-SRTDNN is evaluated with respect to the reference NN-based architectures, showing reductions of 60%, 57.23%, 49.28% and 45.54% compared to the R2TDNN, SARTDNN, VDTDNN and VDLSTM architectures, respectively. Since the CM efficiently captures complex-domain characteristics of the PA with a smaller number of parameters, the NN is required to learn only the residual effects. This significantly reduces the overall model complexity while maintaining accurate characterization of the PA behavior.

In the second scenario, we compare models with a similar number of coefficients (approximately 600) to assess the performance gain of the proposed architectures over the reference ones, as summarized in Table 5. The proposed architectures consistently outperform all the reference models, with the G-SRTDNN achieving the best NMSE performance of -41.13 dB. Specifically, the G-SRTDNN model exhibits performance improvements of 2.72 dB, 2.31 dB, 1.82 dB, 1.11 dB and 1.10 dB over the GMP, R2TDNN, SARTDNN, VDTDNN and VDLSTM architectures, respectively. By effectively learning the complex-domain characteristics of the PA, the proposed models outperform existing real-valued NN-based PA modeling techniques. Consequently,

FIGURE 8. Comparison of performance variation with respect to the number of coefficients for the proposed and reference PA behavioral models.

TABLE 4. Comparison of model complexity required to achieve approximately -40 dB NMSE performance for proposed and reference models.

Model	NMSE (dB)	Num. coeffs	Num. FLOPs
GMP [2]	-38.17	200	798
R2TDNN [14]	-39.09	882	1842
SARTDNN [22]	-39.84	826	2059
VDTDNN [20]	-40.02	696	1836
VDLSTM [21]	-40.03	648	1588
FA-SRTDNN	-40.36	388	1152
G-SRTDNN	-40.35	353	947
PAR-SRTDNN	-40.18	355	887

they achieve higher modeling accuracy for a given model complexity compared to current state-of-the-art approaches.

We now evaluate the impact of the CM memory depth, M_1 , on the overall modeling performance. To isolate this effect and focus specifically on the contribution of the CM, we consider the FA-SRTDNN architecture, without any envelope-dependent features in the NN. Fig. 9 illustrates how the CM memory depth affects the overall modeling performance. As shown, increasing the CM memory depth incrementally enhances the NN’s ability to characterize the NL behavior with fewer neurons. In contrast, without the CM block, the NN requires a significantly larger number of neurons to achieve comparable performance, which clearly demonstrates that incorporating a CM block improves modeling efficiency, and further increasing its memory depth enables more accurate characterization with reduced NN complexity. By allowing the CM to capture part of the memory effects, the residual dynamics that the NN must learn are reduced, resulting in a more compact and effective model.

Signal bandwidth is another key factor affecting modeling performance. We compare the performance of proposed

TABLE 5. Comparison of modeling performance with similar model complexity of approximately 600 coefficients for proposed and reference models.

Model	NMSE (dB)	Num. coeffs	Num. FLOPs
GMP [2]	-38.41	616	2462
R2TDNN [14]	-38.82	629	1313
SARTDNN [22]	-39.31	619	1546
VDTDNN [20]	-40.02	696	1836
VDLSTM [21]	-40.03	648	1588
FA-SRTDNN	-40.97	638	1762
G-SRTDNN	-41.13	629	1631
PAR-SRTDNN	-40.78	631	1571

FIGURE 9. Impact of memory depth of CM on modeling performance for a 100 MHz bandwidth signal. Here, “Without CM block” denotes the NN-only RVTDDN architecture.

and reference models simulating over a range of signal bandwidths from 20 MHz to 100 MHz, as shown in Fig. 10. Higher bandwidths introduce more dynamic distortions due to linear and NL memory effects. It is evident from the figure that the proposed architectures achieve improved modeling performance compared to state-of-the-art models across the considered bandwidths, with a performance gain of at least 1 dB. The Proposed PAR-SRTDNN architecture achieves the best performance, reaching -43.6 dB NMSE at 20 MHz bandwidth. Across all models, performance gradually degrades as the signal bandwidth increases. Notably, SARTDNN shows comparable performance at 20 MHz, but its performance deteriorates at higher bandwidths. This behavior arises because, in the fixed-coefficient SARTDNN training approach, any inaccuracies in the static polynomial model remain uncorrected, forcing the NN to compensate not only for the residual dynamic distortions but also for the static modeling errors of the polynomial model. As the signal bandwidth increases and PA memory effects become stronger, these polynomial errors become more pronounced, making the compensation burden on the NN even larger. Consequently, the overall performance degrades. In contrast,

FIGURE 10. Impact of signal bandwidth on modeling performance.

FIGURE 11. Comparison of the proposed joint training approach and the fixed training approach in SARTDNN.

the proposed joint optimization of CM and NN enables better coefficient adaptation compared to fixing the CM coefficients.

To further evaluate the proposed joint training strategy against the fixed-coefficient approach in [22], we adopt the SARTDNN model with the real-valued CM structure used in [22] and apply the joint training procedure using both random and least-squares coefficient initializations, as described in Section IV. The results are presented in Fig. 11. The joint optimization of both CM and NN coefficients yields up to 1.6 dB improvement over fixing the CM coefficients during training. Least-squares initialization offers slightly better performance than random initialization. When the polynomial coefficients are fixed, any modeling mismatch introduced by the CM block must be compensated solely by the NN, which can limit the achievable modeling accuracy. In contrast, joint optimization allows the CM and NN blocks to adapt together during end-to-end training. In this setting, the polynomial block acts as a trainable structured transformation rather than a static preprocessing stage, enabling a more effective division of modeling tasks between the two components. As a result, the overall system can achieve improved final modeling accuracy compared to sequential or decoupled optimization. Consequently, joint training enhances not only convergence behavior but also the attainable modeling performance.

B. Comparison of Measured Linearization Performance

We employ the architectures and parameters listed in Table 3 to model the DPD and evaluate their linearization performance. The out-of-band and in-band linearization are assessed using ACPR and EVM, defined in (29) and (30), respectively. Table 6 summarizes the measured linearization performance and model complexity for the proposed and reference models. The results demonstrate that the proposed architectures outperform the reference models, achieving an ACPR of below -45 dB and an EVM of below -40 dB.

TABLE 6. Comparison of linearization performance with similar model complexity of approximately 600 coefficients for proposed and reference models.

Model	EVM (dB)	ACPR (dBc)	Num. coeffs	Num. FLOPs
Without DPD	-25.00	-28.81	N/A	N/A
GMP [2]	-37.40	-41.43	200	798
R2TDNN [14]	-38.20	-43.10	629	1313
SARTDNN [22]	-38.68	-43.69	619	1546
VDTDNN [20]	-39.41	-44.36	696	1836
VDLSTM [21]	-39.40	-44.42	648	1588
FA-SRTDNN	-40.31	-45.28	638	1762
G-SRTDNN	-40.47	-45.64	629	1631
PAR-SRTDNN	-40.12	-45.27	631	1571

Among the proposed architectures, G-SRTDNN achieves the best linearization performance, with ACPR of -45.64 dB and EVM of -40.47 dB.

The G-SRTDNN model achieves ACPR improvements of approximately 4.2 dB, 2.54 dB, 1.95 dB, 1.28 dB, and 1.22 dB compared to the GMP, R2TDNN, SARTDNN, VDTDNN, and VDLSTM models, respectively. Similarly, it achieves EVM improvements of around 3.07 dB, 2.27 dB, 1.79 dB, 1.06 dB, and 1.07 dB over the same reference models. As the considered models have approximately the same complexity, the proposed architectures achieve better linearization performance than the state-of-the-art counterparts. Furthermore, as discussed in Section A, the proposed models can achieve comparable or better linearization performance with significantly lower complexity, consistent with the reduction observed in behavioral modeling. These linearization results provide clear evidence that incorporating a simple CM benefits the NN by enabling improved performance with reduced complexity, owing to the complex-domain feature learning that is absent in conventional real-valued approaches. It is also important to note that fully complex-valued systems entail higher training complexity;

FIGURE 12. Measured linearization performance of G-SRTDNN DPD, illustrating the improvement with and without DPD. (a) AM/AM and (b) AM/PM characteristics. (c) PA output power versus PA gain. (d) Constellation diagram.

therefore, using a simple complex-valued polynomial-like model for part of the system while leaving the residual real-valued learning to the NN offers an efficient and effective performance-complexity tradeoff.

Fig. 12 illustrates the linearization performance achieved by the G-SRTDNN DPD model. Fig. 12a and Fig. 12b depict the AM/AM and AM/PM characteristics with and without the DPD, clearly demonstrating its strong linearization capability through effective suppression of both static and dynamic NL effects. Fig. 12c presents the PA output power versus gain, highlighting the preservation of linearity even at higher output power levels. Then, Fig. 12d shows the constellation diagram, where the G-SRTDNN DPD yields a noticeably cleaner and more compact constellation, reflecting the improved in-band signal quality.

Then, Fig. 13 compares the normalized power spectral density (PSD) of the linearized signals, highlighting the out-of-band performance achieved by the considered DPD techniques. The proposed DPD architectures exhibit better out-of-band linearization compared to the conventional GMP and other NN-based DPD approaches. Therefore, these results confirm that the proposed box-oriented framework effectively utilizes the physical characteristics of the PA, resulting in higher in-band and out-of-band linearization performance, either with significantly reduced model complexity compared to all other benchmark models to achieve a given performance, or with higher linearization performance for a given model complexity.

FIGURE 13. Comparison of normalized measured PSD of proposed and reference DPD models.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed three box-oriented architectures that integrate conventional polynomial-based models with NN-based models for PA behavioral modeling and DPD linearization. The proposed architectures, FA-SRTDNN, G-SRTDNN, and PAR-SRTDNN extend our prior work to enable learning of complex-domain PA characteristics. Although each box component can be realized using different configurations, we employed a cross-term memory polynomial for the CM block and a MLP for the NN block without loss of generality. A joint optimization strategy was introduced to enhance the cooperation between the CM and NN blocks. Experimental validation using a 100 MHz OFDM signal and a Skyworks PA demonstrated that the proposed architectures consistently outperform both conventional and NN-based models, achieving either superior modeling accuracy at a given complexity or significant complexity reduction for a target performance level compared to state-of-the-art methods. Moreover, the proposed models exhibited faster convergence and robust performance across different bandwidths. We further confirmed that the joint training approach significantly improves modeling accuracy over fixed-training strategies applied in SRTDNN and SARTDNN. Similar gains were observed in DPD linearization, with notable improvements in ACPR and EVM compared to state-of-the-art techniques. Overall, the proposed box-oriented modeling approach offers a promising direction for transmitter linearization in future 6G systems, where high linearity and low complexity are critical metrics. Future work will explore alternative realizations and orientations of the conventional and NN blocks, extend the framework to capture both long and short-term memory effects, and investigate adaptive training schemes that leverage the linear-in-parameter nature of the polynomial components.

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